

To Assess the Effect of Pneumoperitoneum on Arterial and End Tidal CO₂ Pressure Gradient during Laparoscopic Surgery in Adults: A Prospective Observational Study

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Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 26-07-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: In Laparoscopy the most commonly used gas for Pneumoperitoneum is carbon dioxide. Capnography is a non-invasive method of continuously measuring ET_{CO₂}, which reflects Pa_{CO₂}. This study was done to see how Pneumoperitoneum affects the Pa_{CO₂}-ET_{CO₂} gradient during laparoscopic appendectomy and cholecystectomy in adults.

Material and Methods: Sixty ASA status 1 and 2 patients of both sexes, 20 to 60 years of age undergoing elective laparoscopic appendectomy or laparoscopic cholecystectomy were chosen in a prospective observational study, conducted at tertiary care centre, Vijayawada after approval from institutional ethics committee, between January 2021– June 2022. Patient data was analysed for Systolic blood pressure, Diastolic blood pressure, mean arterial blood pressure, End tidal CO₂ (mmHg), Pa_{CO₂}(mmHg), pH, Bicarbonate, Pa_{CO₂}-ET_{CO₂}(mmHg) gradient and Peak airway pressure (cmH₂O).

Results: There was significant increase in mean arterial blood pressure, heart rate, end tidal carbon dioxide and Pa_{CO₂}, but was clinically within normal range. There was significant increase in Pa_{CO₂}-ET_{CO₂} gradient after CO₂ insufflation but within normal range. There was significant increase in peak airway pressure after CO₂ insufflation.

Conclusion: The arterial and end tidal carbon dioxide pressure gradients are normal even after CO₂ Pneumoperitoneum in ASA 1 and 2 patients. The normal Pa_{CO₂}-ET_{CO₂} pressure gradient implies adequate ventilation to alveoli and perfusion (blood flow to pulmonary capillaries). Hence end tidal Capnography and pulse oximetry can be used as non-invasive techniques for monitoring CO₂ elimination and arterial oxygenation during laparoscopic surgery patients.

Keywords: Laparoscopy, Pa_{CO₂}, ET_{CO₂}, insufflation, Peak airway pressure.

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Introduction

Laparoscopy is a minimally invasive surgery that allows endoscopic access to the peritoneal cavity after insufflation of gas to create a space between the anterior abdominal wall and viscera for safe instrument and organ manipulation.

The advantages of laparoscopy include reduced post-operative pain and ileus, better cosmetic results and shorter hospital stay. The most commonly used gas for Pneumoperitoneum is carbon dioxide [1].

CO₂ has proven to be superior because it is non-flammable, inert, non-irritant, and readily available. It is quickly buffered in the blood by bicarbonate and excreted through the lungs. Carbon dioxide absorption from the pressurized Pneumoperitoneum

causes clinically significant cardiopulmonary and hemodynamic changes. Carbon dioxide is 20 times more soluble than oxygen, which is insufflated at 10 to 12 mmHg. Capnography is a noninvasive method of continuously measuring ET_{CO₂}, which reflects Pa_{CO₂}.

In healthy people, the difference between arterial and end-tidal carbondioxide levels range from 2 to 5 mmHg. Capnography monitoring can provide vital respiratory parameters in intubated patients in a reliable and quantitative manner [2].

Changes in carbon dioxide concentration in expired gas can also reflect changes in cardiac output, pulmonary blood flow distribution, and metabolic activity. The observation of an increase in Pa_{CO₂}

when CO₂ is used as an insufflating agent but not when nitrous oxide or helium are used suggests that the mechanism of increased PaCO₂ during CO₂ Pneumoperitoneum is due to CO₂ absorption rather than mechanical ventilator repercussions of increased intra-abdominal pressure. There are 2 ways to measure ETCO₂, 1. Side stream analyser 2.

Main stream analyser. In the present study, the effects of Pneumoperitoneum on PaCO₂-ETCO₂ gradient during laparoscopic appendicectomy and cholecystectomy were analysed [3].

Ethics Committee: Certificate Reference Number: IEC/2021/002/SMC-2021

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICS COMMITTEE
Siddhartha Medical College & Govt General Hospital (IEC SMC & GGH)
(Authorized by govt Siddhartha Medical College & Govt General Hospitals)
Govt Siddhartha Medical College Campus, Ring Road, Gunadala, Vijayawada -520008, Andhra Pradesh, India
Registration Number: ECR\633\INST\AP\2014\RR-19

Communication of Decision of Ethics Committee SMC & GGH

Reference Number: IEC\2021\002\SMC

Date: 04-03-2021

Protocol Title	A PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY TO ASSESS THE EFFECT OF PNEUMOPERITONEUM ON ARTERIAL AND END TIDAL CARBONDIOXIDE PRESSURE GRADIENT DURING LAPAROSCOPIC SURGERY IN ADULTS
Investigator Name	Dr. GOGINENI SAISREE
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Department Name	ANAESTHESIOLOGY
Institute Name	SIDDHARTHA MEDICAL COLLEGE, NEAR Dr Y.S.R UNIVERSITY OF HEALTH SCIENCES, GUNADALA, VIJAYAWADA-520008, ANDHRA PRADESH, INDIA
Review Type	FULL REVIEW
Date of Review Meeting	03-03-2021
Decision of the IEC SMC & GGH	APPROVED
Comments	NIL

MEMBER SECRETARY, V.V. Radhika
5/3/2021
IEC SMC & GGH-Vijayawada.

Govt Siddhartha Medical College Associated Hospitals:

- ❖ New Govt General Hospital, Govt. Siddhartha Medical College Campus Gunadala, Vijayawada-520008, Andhra Pradesh, India.
- ❖ Old Govt Hospital, Two Town, Hanumanpet, Vijayawada-520002, Andhra Pradesh, India.
- ❖ Yarlagadda Venkanna Chowdary oncology wing & Research Center [YVCOW], Chinnakakani, Guntur -522503 AP India.

Figure 1: Ethics Committee Certificate

Materials and Methods: It is a prospective randomized controlled trial conducted at tertiary care center, Vijayawada after approval from ethics committee. Sixty ASA status 1 and 2 patients of both sexes between the ages of 20 and 60 undergoing elective laparoscopic appendicectomy or laparoscopic cholecystectomy lasting at least 45 minutes were chosen.

Inclusion Criteria

- ASA physical status 1 & 2 Patients

- Patients having a laparoscopic cholecystectomy or appendectomy.
- elective surgery
- Body Mass Index (BMI): 25 kg/m²
- pt with valid and informed consent

Exclusion Criteria:

- The patient does not meet the inclusion criteria.
- Previous history of hemorrhagic diathesis and clotting disorder

- Patients with respiratory diseases such as chronic bronchitis, emphysema, bronchial asthma, and respiratory failure.
- Cardiovascular disease
- Renal insufficiency
- Known drug allergy or sensitivity
- Patient posted for emergency procedure

Drugs to Be Kept Ready:

Inj .glycopyrrolate 0.2 mg ampoules, inj. Fentanyl 50 Mcgs /ml ampoules, inj. propofol vials 1%, Inj. Succinyl choline hydrochloride vial, inj .atracurium vials, inj. Neostigmine ampoules, sevoflurane,

Procedure:

Patients were advised to fast for 8 hours overnight, were given T. alprazolam 0.5 mg the night before surgery. On the morning of surgery, 150 mg of Ranitidine and 10 mg of Metaclopramide was given. After being transferred to the operating room, the right cephalic vein was cannulated with an 18 G iv cannula and ringer lactate was started. Baseline values were obtained by measuring heart rate, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, mean arterial pressure, peak airway pressure, and ETCO₂.

All patients were premedicated with inj Glycopyrrolate.2mg iv. For analgesia, patients were given inj fentanyl 2 Mcgs/kg, induced with Inj propofol 2 mg/kg, and paralyzed with inj Succinyl choline 1.5 mg/kg. After adequate relaxation, the patients were intubated with an appropriate size endotracheal tube and connected to a GE ventilator with a tidal volume of 8 ml/kg and a respiratory rate of 12 to 14 /min, oxygen and nitrous oxide at 1.5 L/min and 3 L/min, respectively, and sevoflurane 1% -2%.15 minutes after insufflation, an arterial blood sample was taken and sent for analysis, vitals were measured and noted. Throughout the procedure, intra-abdominal pressure was kept between 10 and 12 mmHg. After the surgery has been completed and adequate respiratory efforts, patient was reversed with injections of Neostigmine 50 mcgs/kg and glycopyrrolate 10 mcgs/kg. After regaining adequate muscle power and reflexes, the patient was extubated after proper oral suctioning.

Parameters Measured

- Heart rate(beats/min)
- Systolic blood pressure(mmHg)
- Diastolic blood pressure(mmHg)
- Mean arterial blood pressure (mmHg)
- End tidal CO₂ (mmHg)
- PaCO₂(mmHg)
- pH

- Bicarbonate (mmHg)
- P(a-ET)CO₂ mmHg pressure gradient
- Peak airway pressure

Results and Observations:

Main Objective:

To determine and compare the relationship of arterial carbondioxide and end tidal carbondioxide pressure gradient before and after CO₂ Pneumoperitoneum.

Other Objectives

- To determine the hemodynamic changes (pulse rate, systolic, diastolic blood pressure, mean arterial blood pressure) during laparoscopy.
- To determine the peak airway pressure changes and acid base changes (pH, Hco₃) during laparoscopy.

Normal values:

- EtCO₂ 35-45mmHg
- PaCO₂ 35-45mmHg
- pH 7.35-7.45
- HCO₃:22-24 mmHg
- PaCO₂-etCO₂ gradient 2-5 mmHg

A sample of 60 patients was taken for the study. Data was expressed as mean \pm SD. statistical analysis was with student's t test .A p value < 0.05 was considered significant. The age distribution is between 20 and 46 years. The mean is 30.25 and the standard deviation is 6.398. p value is 0.06 , which is insignificant. out of 60 patients 55% (33) were males and remaining 45%(27) were females. The mean duration of surgery for 60 patients is 36 minutes, the minimum duration is 25 minutes and maximum is 45 minutes. Standard deviation is 6.815.

ANALYSIS (STUDENT t TEST) Independent Samples Test

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances

Systolic BP before & after CO₂ Insufflation: P value > 0.05 which is statistically insignificant.

Diastolic BP before & after CO₂ insufflation: P value is 0.000, less than 0.05. Hence is significant.

Mean BP: P value is 0.00 which is < .05, hence statistically significant.

For heart rate before and after insufflation, p value is 0.00 is statistically significant.Comparison of pacO₂ before co₂ insufflation

Etc o₂ after co₂ insufflation p value is 0.001, which is less than .05, thus it is significant.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics (mean and standard deviation)

	N	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	60	46	30.25	6.398
Valid N(list wise)	60			

Table 2: Sex distribution shows out 60 patients 55% (33) patients were males and the remaining 45% (27) were females.

Valid		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Male	33	55.0	55.0	55.0
	Female	27	45.0	45.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Table 3:

Duration Of Surgery					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	CumulativePercent
Valid	25	7	11.7	11.7	11.7
	30	15	25	25	36.7
	35	11	18.3	18.3	55
	40	13	21.7	21.7	76.7
	45	14	23.3	23.3	100
	Total	60	100	100	

The minimum duration is 25 minutes and maximum is 45 minutes. The mean duration of surgery for 60 patients is 36 minutes and the standard deviation is 6.815.

Table 4: Systolic BP before Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean	117.6	
Std. Deviation	7.567	

Table 5: Systolic BP 15 min after co2 insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean	124.17	
Std. Deviation	8.447	

Table 6: Systolic BP before & after CO2 Insufflation

Group Statistics					
	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Sys_BP	1	60	117.63		
	2	60	124.17	7.567	.977

Table 7: Independent Samples Test Analysis (Student t Test)

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means						
			Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
								Lower	Upper
Sys_BP	Equal variances assumed	1.000		118	0.130.	-6.533		.	.
	Equal variance s not assumed		.	.	.	-6.533	.	.	.

P value > 0.05 which is statistically insignificant.

Table 8: Diastolic BP before Co2 Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean	70.80	
Std. Deviation	5.339	

Table 9: Diastolic BP 15Mins after Co2 Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean	77.13	
Std. Deviation	5.583	

Table 10: Diastolic BP Before & After Co2 Insufflation

Group Statistics					
	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Dias_BP	1	60	70.80	5.339	.689
	2	60	77.13	5.583	.721

Table 11:

Independent Samples Test											
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means							
		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
										Lower	Upper
dias_bp	Equal variances assumed	.055	.860	-6.351	118	.000	-6.333	.997	-8.308	-4.359	
	Equal variances not assumed			-6.351	117.765	.000	-6.333	.997	-8.308	-4.358	

p value is 0.000, less than 0.05. Significant

Table 12(A): Mean Blood Pressure before Co2 Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean	86	
Std. deviation	5.00	

Table 12(B): Mean Blood Pressure after Co2 Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean	92.790	
Std. Deviation	4.9463	

Table 13: Mean BP Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means							
		F	Sig.	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
										Lower	Upper
Mean BP	Equal variances assumed	.014	.906	7.074	118	.000	6.416667	.9070769	8.2129259	4.6204074	

	Equal vari- ancesnot assumed			7.07 4	117.99 1	.000	6.416666 7	.9070769	8.212927 3	4.620406 0
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p value is 0.00 which is < .05, statistically significant.

Table 14(A): Descriptive statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pulse Rate Before Insufflation	60	77.83	11.218
PR After Insufflation	60	81.78	11.213
Valid N (list wise)	60		

Table 14(B): Independent sample test for heart rate

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
HR	Equal vari- ances assumed	4.385	.038	1.9290	118	.000	-3.9500	2.048	-8.0049	0.10493
	Equal vari- ances not assumed			1.9290	118	.000	-3.9500	2.048	-8.0049	0.10493

P value is 0.00, statistically significant

Table 15: EtCo₂ before CO₂ Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean	32.77	
Std. Deviation	1.835	

Table 16: ETCO₂ after CO₂ Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean	37.08	
Std. Deviation	1.499	

Table 17: EtcO₂ Before & After CO₂ Insufflation Group Statistics

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
EtcO ₂	1	60	32.77	1.835	.237
	2	60	37.08	1.499	.194

Table 18: Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
EtcO ₂	Equal vari- ances as- sumed	4.342	.039	-14.110	118	.000	-4.317	.306	-4.922	3.711
	Equal vari- ances not assumed			-14.110	113.476	.000	-4.317	.306	-4.923	-3.711

p value is 0.001, which is less than .05, thus it is significant.

Table 19: PacO2 before Co2 Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean		36.52
Std. Deviation		2.077

Table 20: Paco2 after Co2 Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean		41.36
Std. Deviation		1.562

Table 21: Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Pa-CO2	Equal variances assumed	4.385	.038	-14.424	118	.000	-4.838	.335	-5.503	-4.174
	Equal variances not assumed			14.424	109.557	.000	-4.838	.335	-5.503	-4.174

p value is less than 0.05, which is statistically significant

Table 22: Paco2 – EtcO2 Pressure Gradient before Co2 Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean		3.75
Std. Deviation		1.146

Table 23: Paco2 – EtcO2 Gradient after Co2 Insufflation

	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean		4.27
Std. Deviation		.935

Table 24: PACO2- ETCO2, Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Pa-CO2-	variances assumed	.118	.732	-2.732	118	.007	-.5216667	.1909771	-.8998534	-.1434799
EtCO2										
diff	Equal variances not assumed			-2.732	113.432	.007	-.5216667	.1909771	-.9000112	-.1433221

p value is 0.007, less than 0.05, statistically significant.

Table 25: Peak Airway Pressure before CO2 Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean		14.47
Std. Deviation		1.90

Table 26: Peak Airway Pressure after Co2 Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean		17.32
Std. Deviation		1.836

Table 27: Peak Airway Pressure Before and After Insufflation.

	group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. ErrorMean
Peak airway Pres- sure	1	60	14.47	1.900	.245
	2	60	17.32	1.836	.237

Table 28: Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
peakair way_PR	Equal vari- ancesassumed	.170	.681	-8.355	118	.000	-2.850	.341	-3.526	-2.174
	Equal vari- ances not assumed			8.355	117.865	.000	-2.850	.341	-3.526	2.174

p value is 0.00 , statistically significant.

Table 29: pH Before Co2 Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean		7.40
Std. Deviation		.022

Table 30: pH After Co2 Insufflation

N	Valid	60
	Missing	0
Mean		7.360
Std. Deviation		.012

Table 31:

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
pH	Equal variances	31.027	.000	11.374	118	.000	.037	.003	.030	.043

	assumed									
	Equal variances not assumed			11.374	90.663	.000	.037	.003	.030	.043

p value is 0.000, less than 0.05 , statistically significant

Table 32: Bicarbonate Before and After Co2 Insufflation:

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
HCO3 BI	60	24	26	25.05	.516
HCO3 AI	60	24	26	24.52	.372
Valid N (list wise)	60				

Table 33: Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means							
			Sig.	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
HCO	Equal variances assumed	1.000		118	0.30.	.527			.	.
	Equal variances not assumed	527			.	.

p value is 0.30 , > 0.05. statistically insignificant

Figure 1: Capnogram

Figure 2:

Figure 3: Sex Distribution

Figure 4: Duration of Surgery

Figure 5: PaCo2 values before and after insufflation

Figure 6: ETCo2 values before and after co2 insufflation

Discussion

During laparoscopic surgery, carbon dioxide Pneumoperitoneum is created resulting in hypercarbia which has complex effects on various systems of body.

Hemodynamic Effects: The present study demonstrates that the intra-abdominal pressure of 12 mmHg maintained for laparoscopic surgery induces hemodynamic changes characterized by increase in heart rate, mean arterial blood pressure and peripheral vascular resistance. [6]Gupta Shobhana et al studied the changes in vital parameters during laparoscopic surgery. The heart normally tolerates an increase of after load easily, but becomes sensitive to changes in after load in a compensated state when it is subjected to Pneumoperitoneum [7]. These results indicate the need for caution in pa-

tients with impaired cardiac function, anemia or hypovolemia scheduled for laparoscopic surgery. Similar to present study, [8] JORIS et al demonstrated during laparoscopic surgery, both mechanical and humoral factors contribute to increase in systemic vascular resistance. They explained that decrease in the cardiac output is caused by a reduction in venous return or increased Systemic vascular resistance. Cardiac output was decreased to a maximum of 28% at an insufflation pressure of 15 mmHg. The cardiac output further reduced when the intra-abdominal pressure exceeds 20 mmHg these data suggest that it is prudent to reduce the rate of insufflation and limit abdominal inflating pressures to minimum. [9] V.Muralidhar studied physiology of Pneumoperitoneum and anaesthesia in laparoscopic surgery. He postulated increased systemic vascular resistance, increased mean arteri-

al pressure, and minimal increase in heart rate during Pneumoperitoneum. Results of present study are similar to the above study.

Heart rate: It has Statistical significance. The mean heart rate pre insufflation was 77.83, and 15 minutes after insufflation was 81.78 and p value is less than 0.05, thus statistically significant.

Clinical significance: Increase in heart rate is caused by CO₂ Pneumoperitoneum, which is in accordance to [8] Joris et al and [9] Muralidhar et al studies.

Systolic blood pressure: The mean systolic blood pressure before insufflation is 117.63 mmHg and during insufflation is 124.17 mmHg and the p value is 0.130, statistically insignificant.

The systolic blood pressure varied from 126.56±6.45 mm Hg preoperatively to 129.55±8.65 mm Hg post operatively, where the p value is 0.1345 that is insignificant. This result is in accordance with the present study.

Diastolic blood pressure: The mean diastolic blood pressure is 70.80 mmHg before CO₂.

Pneumoperitoneum and 77.13 mmHg during the insufflation, p value of 0.00 is statistically significant.

7 GUPTA SHOBHANA et al also studied diastolic blood pressure changes, which was 77.48 ± 3.44mmHg preoperatively and 80.08±3.46mmHg post operatively, the p value was 0.004 statistically significant, and this result is similar to present study which has the p value 0.00, highly significant though both values are within normal range clinically.

Mean arterial blood pressure: There is statistically significant (p value 0.00) increase in mean arterial blood pressure during Pneumoperitoneum. The mean pre insufflation mean arterial blood pressure was 86 mmHg and 15 minutes after insufflation was 92.790 mmHg., which is in accordance with 8JORIS et al, [18] Makwana et al.

Alterations in cardiac rhythm may also be seen during laparoscopy and are related to increased intra-abdominal pressure, hypercarbia and surgical stimulation. As the intra-abdominal pressure was maintained between 10-12 mmHg, none of the patients developed intra operative arrhythmias.

[10] D.B. SCOTT and D.G. JULIAN stated that the incidence of cardiac arrhythmias was more in patients who received carbondioxide to inflate the abdomen compared to nitrous oxide. [11] WITTGEN et al studied that patients with preoperative cardiopulmonary disease showed significant increase in arterial blood pressure and decrease in pH during CO₂ Pneumoperitoneum compared with patients without underlying disease. Patients with

compromised cardiopulmonary function were excluded in the present study.

Respiratory System

[12] TAN and [7] HIROVEN et al, proposed an increase in tidal volume rather than respiratory rate controls hypercarbia efficiently. Also [12] P.L.TAN, T.L.LEE, et al demonstrated an increase in tidal volume is sufficient to eliminate excess CO₂ and maintain normal pulmonary oxygenation.

Therefore, in present study tidal volume 10 ml/kg and respiratory rate 12-14 /min was maintained

ETCO₂ AND PaCO₂

ETCO₂ increased from 32.77 to 37.08 mmHg, and PaCO₂ increased from 36.52 to 41.36 mmHg respectively during the procedure, and the p value is < 0.05 for both. Thus it is statistically significant, but the ETCO₂ and the PaCO₂ were under clinically normal range. According to [13] MULLET et al rapid rise in PaCO₂ and ETCO₂ occurs within 10 minutes of insufflation. Data was taken after 15 minute of CO₂ insufflation. Similar to the findings of [13] MULLET et al, [14] MEININGER et al, [11] SHIKAWA et al and [15] MONAGLE et al, there was a progressive increase in ETCO₂ and PaCO₂ during CO₂ insufflation in present study. The maximum rate of increase in CO₂ occurred in the first 15 minutes, there after increase in carbon dioxide reached plateau and remained the same for 15- 45 minutes. A correlation between PaCO₂ and ETCO₂ was observed in present study.

This is similar to findings of [16] Nyarwaya et al and [2] Baraka et al who also noted a correlation between the PaCO₂ and ETCO₂. [17] P. PELOSI et al found that abdominal insufflation during laparoscopic surgery causes markedly reduced static compliance of the respiratory system, lung and chest wall and to a lesser amount lung volume. However during laparoscopy PaCO₂ increases, which closely correlates with PETCO₂. Consequently P(a-et) co₂ gradient will not change. In present study, Oxygen saturation did not significantly alter during abdominal insufflation.

P(a-ET) GRADIENT: The mean difference of PaCO₂ and ETCO₂ pressure gradient was 3.75 mmHg , before insufflation and the mean difference of PaCO₂ and ETCO₂ pressure gradient after Pneumoperitoneum was 4.27mmHg. In healthy patients with normal ventilation-perfusion ratio, the pressure gradient is 2-5 mmHg. The p value for PaCO₂ and ETCO₂ gradient was 0.007, statistically significant. In present study, although the p value is statistically significant, it was within normal physiological range and similar with [2] BARAKA et al, [16] NYARWAYA et al, [3] BHAVANI SHANKAR et al studies.

pH and Bicarbonate: The mean pH before Pneumoperitoneum was 7.40 and the mean pH after Pneumoperitoneum was 7.36. pH significantly decreased after 15 minutes, and the p value is 0.00, less than 0.05. Statistically significant. The present study is similar to [33] D.T.T. TRAN et al that showed CO₂ insufflation lowered the p H to 7.31 from 7.40 which was statistically highly significant with p value <0.001. The mean bicarbonate before and during CO₂ insufflation is 25.05 mmHg and 24.52 mmHg and the p value is 0.30 statistically insignificant. 18Se-yuan Liu et al demonstrated that ETCO₂ and PaCO₂ increased from 31.4 ±0.7 mmHg to 42.1±1.6 mmHg and 33.3 ±0.7 mmHg to 43.7±1.2 mmHg respectively, during the course of the procedure. Arterial p H decreased from 7.43±0.01 mmHg to 7.34±0.01 mmHg, while bicarbonate concentration remains same, similar to present study.

Peak Airway Pressure: The mean peak airway pressure before insufflation was 14.47 cmH₂O and the mean of peak airway pressure after Pneumoperitoneum was 17.32 cmH₂O. The p value is 0.00 (<0.05) statistically significant.

Summary

The effects of pneumo peritoneum on P(a-et) co₂ gradient during laparoscopic surgery were studied. There is no significant difference in the age and sex of the patients. There is no significant difference in duration of surgery. There is no significant increase in systolic blood pressure but there is significant increase in diastolic blood pressure. There is significant increase in mean arterial blood pressure. There is significant increase in heart rate. There is significant increase in end tidal carbon dioxide after co₂insufflation, but it is clinically within normal range. There is significant increase in PaCO₂ after CO₂ insufflation but the increase is less than 45 mmHg. There is significant increase in PaCO₂-ETCO₂ gradient after CO₂ insufflation. But the pressure gradients are within normal range.

There is significant decrease in pH, but bicarbonate measurements remained unchanged.

There is significant increase in peak airway pressure after CO₂ insufflation.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrated that during laparoscopic cholecystectomy or, appendicectomy, abdominal carbondioxide insufflation causes increase in ETCO₂ and Pa CO₂ significantly higher than Pre insufflation value but within physiological range. A correlation was observed between the PaCO₂ and ETCO₂ throughout duration of insufflation. ETCO₂ can be used as an index of PaCO₂ with the provision that the clinician be aware that an increased P(a-ET)CO₂ gradient reflects reduced cardiac output. The arterial and end tidal carbon

dioxide pressure gradients are under the normal limits even after CO₂ pneumo peritoneum in ASA 1 and 2 patients. The normal pressure P(a-ET) CO₂ gradient implies adequate ventilation to alveoli and perfusion (blood flow to pulmonary capillaries). This results suggest that end tidal Capnography and pulse oximetry can be used as noninvasive techniques for monitoring CO₂ elimination and arterial oxygenation during laparoscopic surgery in ASA1 and 2 patients.

The age distribution is between 20 and 46 years. The mean is 30.25 and the standard deviation is 6.398. p value is 0.06, which is insignificant.

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